

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF A VERTICAL AXIS THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADE

K. A. Brown* and R. Brooks
Division of Materials, Mechanics and Structures
Faculty of Engineering
University of Nottingham
University Park
Nottingham NG7 2RD, United Kingdom
*Email Address: kevin.brown@nottingham.ac.uk

SUMMARY

This paper describes the design, analysis and manufacture of a vertical axis thermoplastic composite wind turbine blade. The design featured a sandwich construction with thermoplastic composite skins and a thermoplastic foam core. Structural and modal analyses have been conducted using advanced finite element methods. Structural validation tests were performed on a sub-scale prototype.

Keywords: Wind turbine blade, thermoplastic composite, finite element analysis, structural design and analysis, sandwich structures.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing concerns over pollution from current energy sources, especially oil and coal, along with apprehensions over a potential energy deficit in the future has led to a focus on sustainable renewable energy sources such as wind energy. The European Union (EU) has set renewable targets that are expected to drive significant increases in the use of wind turbines across its member states. In particular, the UK has been set a target of 15% of its overall energy to come from renewal sources by 2015 [1]. It is anticipated that at least 75% of this will be generated from wind energy [1]. Today, the wind energy market is dominated by horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTS). HAWTS tend to work best in more open settings, offshore or on land in rural areas where the wind is not disturbed by buildings or trees. In contrast, vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTS) are more suited for built-up urban areas. They have lower wind start-up speeds, can be located nearer to the ground making maintenance easier, work in any wind direction and are relatively quiet. However, market penetration has been slow due in part to their high cost. In order for VAWTS to become more attractive to consumers and governments; manufacturers will have to make them more affordable, efficient, durable and sustainable.

In light of this, predictive finite element analysis methods and manufacturing processes for vertical axis wind turbine blades made from thermoplastic composite sandwich (TPS) material systems are being developed at the University of Nottingham. TPSs offer several advantages including: high fracture toughness and impact tolerance, high fatigue resistance and good specific mechanical properties. In addition, TPSs offer the

opportunity for one-step, low cost, clean manufacturing (no styrene emissions). Furthermore, they can be recycled at end of life.

This paper presents the preliminary results of a feasibility study on the use of a one-step vacuum moulded TPS material system for a 5 kW vertical axis wind turbine blade. The design, finite element analysis and manufacturing processes are described.

GENERAL DESIGN

The proposed blade construction is a sandwich structure with thermoplastic glass reinforced composite skins and a thermoplastic foam core. The skin laminates are manufactured using Twintex™ commingled woven fabric E-glass/polypropylene material with a 60% fibre weight fraction [2]. The core material is a lightweight polyethylene terephthalate (PET) foam core of density 150 kg/m^3 [3]. In the proposed blade design, the aerofoil profile has a constant chord (0.44 m) along the length of the blade (4 m). The blade has two connection points on one of its broadsides for assembly to the rotor through supporting struts (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Vertical axis wind turbine [4].

The initial blade design was evaluated through analysis, manufacture and testing of a sub-scale prototype blade with a scaling ratio of $\frac{1}{2}$ for the chord and $\frac{1}{4}$ for the length as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Geometry of the full and sub-scale blade model.

MANUFACTURE

The sub-scale prototype blade was manufactured using a one-step vacuum moulding process. Vacuum consolidation was selected because it is a relatively simple, low cost, out of autoclave process for manufacturing thermoplastic composite sandwich constructions [5]. The first step was to machine the foam core to the shape of the aerofoil using a CNC milling machine as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. (a) CNC machining of PET foam core to aerofoil shape (b) complete core.

The vacuum moulding process steps are shown in Figure 4. Three plies of Twintex™ were laid-up over the foam in a $[0/90]_3$ orientation and held in place by using a flat tip soldering iron to bond the edges. It should be noted that this layup sequence does not necessarily reflect the actual lay-up for the final blade design but was selected for material-design verification purposes. The laid-up blade is then wrapped with a nylon film followed by breather fabric. The nylon film prevents the breather fabric from adhering to the composite skin during consolidation. This assembly is then placed in a large nylon vacuum bag. The open ends of the vacuum bag are sealed and a vacuum is applied that holds the materials in place as the blade is transferred to the bottom female mould. The mould is closed by bolting the top female mould into position. The full mould assembly is placed in the hot air oven as shown in Figure 4. The temperature in the top and bottom surface of the mould was measured using thermocouples and a LabView™ data acquisition system. The blade was consolidated at 200 °C under vacuum (0.1 MPa). The process temperature cycle is shown in Figure 5. The required process temperature of 200 °C is reached after 3 hours. The part is maintained at this temperature for just over an hour to obtain good consolidation and then cooled to room temperature slowly overnight. The demoulded blade is shown in Figure 6. The process has not been optimised to minimise cycle time, e.g. by forced mould cooling, but had the objective of producing a well consolidated part.

Figure 4. Pictures showing the manufacturing process (a) Twintex plies laid-up over foam core, (b) sandwich wrapped with nylon film, (c) breather fabric placed around sandwich, (d) sandwich placed in vacuum bag and air evacuated, (e) sandwich placed in female mould (f) mould closed and placed in hot air oven. The blade is heated to 200 °C and compacted at a pressure of 0.1 MPa.

Figure 5. Process cycle for vacuum consolidation of sub-scale prototype blade in a hot air oven.

Figure 6. Picture of demoulded thermoplastic composite sandwich blade.

STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

Structural Testing

The structural response of the sub-scale prototype blade was assessed using a three-point bending test. The bending test was conducted on an Instron universal test machine at a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. The test setup is shown in Figure 7. The blade is clamped at both ends, with profiled clamps, over a span of 850 mm. Cylindrical steel rollers of 25 mm diameter are attached to the clamps. The rollers sit in V grooves on uprights which prevent all translational movement and only allow rotation around the axis of the rollers (y-axis). A loading head having the shape of the top half of the aerofoil was used to apply load to the centre of the blade until failure occurred.

Finite Element Modelling

A finite element model of the sub-scale blade three-point bending test was developed. The geometry of the wind turbine blade was created using the Pro-Engineer™ solid modelling software and then imported into HyperMesh™ for meshing (see Figure 8). The mesh was imported to the LS-DYNA™ finite element software for analysis. Simplified boundary conditions were applied as depicted in Figure 8. The supporting clamps were represented by two sets of nodes that were constrained for translations in the y and z directions and rotations around the x and z axes. A ramped velocity was distributed along a set of top nodes in the centre of the blade to simulate the loading of the blade.

The Twintex™ skins were modelled with Belytschko-Tsay 4-node shell elements whereas the foam core was modelled with 8-node hexahedral solid elements. The LS-DYNA™ MAT58 composite material model was used to represent the Twintex material. The MAT58 model is an anisotropic damage model that is based on the Matzenmiller formulation [6] where a set of internal damage variables are used to describe the evolution of damage through the degradation of the material stiffness. The model is capable of simulating fibre fracture (tensile/compression) and in-plane matrix damage.

The PET foam core was modelled with the LS-DYNA™ MAT57 isotropic foam material model. Material parameters for MAT58 and MAT57 were obtained from previous work [7].

Figure 7. Picture of three-point bending test setup.

Figure 8. Three-bending test finite element model (a) mesh (b) boundary conditions.

Results

Figure 9 shows a comparison of the experimental and simulation force-displacement curves for the sub-scale blade. There is an initial elastic response up to the peak load followed by an abrupt load drop of 66% of the maximum value to a near constant plateau load. The simulation curve shows good correlation with the overall shape of the test curve. However, the load drop after the reaching the maximum load was not as abrupt as observed in the test. The predicted peak load (4.42 kN) and displacement at peak load (25 mm) agree well with experimental results, 4.4 kN and 28 mm, respectively.

A comparison of the experimental and predicted damage in the blade is shown in Figure 9. The predicted macro-scale damage included compression fibre fracture and matrix damage at the centre of the top skin and leading edge near the loading head shows good qualitative agreement with the test observations. However, the model was not able to accurately predict the final failure in the form of splitting, skin-core debonding and buckling that occurred at the trailing edge adjacent to the loading head, as depicted in Figure 10. This is because a perfect bond between the skin and core was assumed in the model. Nevertheless, the model's overall performance has been validated over a suitable loading range and can confidently be used for the predictive analysis of the full-scale blade over its operating region.

Figure 9. Comparison of experimental and simulation results (a) force-displacement curves (b) fibre and matrix damage (c) predicted fibre fracture (d) predicted matrix damage.

Figure 10. (a) delamination, skin-core debonding and buckling at trailing edge adjacent to loading head (b) predicted localized buckling at trailing edge.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF FULL-SCALE BLADE

Following validation of the finite element material models using the sub-scale prototype blade simulations and tests, an analysis of the modal and structural response of the full-scale blade was conducted as described below.

Modal Analysis

In the course of designing the blade, vibration has to be considered as it is important to avoid dynamic instability in the form of resonance, where there is coincidence between the natural frequency of the blade and the rotational frequency. Resonance can cause

fatigue damage and rapid failure [8]. Modal analysis of the full scale wind turbine blade was conducted using the implicit solver in the LS-DYNA™ finite element code. Figure 11 shows the mesh and boundary conditions for the finite element model of the blade. Two groups of nodes in the location of the strut connection joints were fully constrained for all translations and rotations, representing a rigid attachment to the struts. The skin and core were modelled with 4-node shell elements and 8-node solid elements, respectively. An orthotropic elastic material model was used to model the Twintex™ composite material while the PET foam was modelled with an isotropic elastic material model. The skin laminate comprised 6 plies of Twintex™ with a $[0/90]_6$ layup.

Figure 11. Mesh and boundary conditions for modal analysis.

Table 1 shows the first five natural frequencies and their mode shapes for the blade. The first three mode shapes are characterised by flapwise bending while the fourth and fifth mode exhibited torsional deformation. The corresponding mode shapes for first and fourth modes are shown in Figure 12.

A Campbell diagram [8], shown in Figure 13, was used to identify any possible resonance between the operational speed and the blade natural frequencies. In all cases the rotor rotational frequency (P1) and its multiple for 2 bladed rotors (P2) are never in conflict with the natural frequencies of the blade. This initial analysis has shown that the fundamental frequency of the blade (27.27 Hz) is also sufficiently high to avoid resonance with the natural frequency of the tower which is typically about 1 Hz [9].

Table 1. Modal analysis of wind turbine blade.

Mode	Natural Frequency (Hz)	Mode Shape
1	27.27	First flapwise bending
2	29.31	Second flapwise bending
3	52.16	Third flapwise bending
4	102.15	First torsional
5	103.01	Second torsional

Figure 12. Mode shapes (a) 1st mode shape (b) 4th mode shape.

Figure 13. Campbell diagram for the thermoplastic composite sandwich blade.

Load Cases

In operation, the blade will be subjected to various load combinations including aerodynamic, gravitational and centrifugal loads. For evaluation of the blade design, simulations were conducted for two load cases: 1) storm conditions with high wind speeds for a stationary turbine (blades broadside to wind) and 2) loss of load due to disconnection from the grid. The finite element models for the load case analysis have the same mesh and boundary conditions for the strut joints as applied in the modal model. In addition, for case 1, acceleration due to gravity was applied to all nodes in a vertical direction along the length of the blade while a transverse wind force was evenly distributed along the nodes on the broadside of the blade that has the strut joint connection points. In case 2, acceleration due to gravity and transverse centrifugal load was applied to all nodes in addition to a wind force which was evenly distributed in the transverse direction along the nodes on the broadside of the blade. The MAT 58 and 57 material models are used to model the skin and foam, respectively, using the same material parameters as in the sub-scale model.

Table 2 summarises the results for both load case simulations. Case 2 represents the worse case loading for the wind turbine blade. Figure 14 shows the stresses in the Twintex™ skin in the fibre direction (0°) along the length of the blade for case 2. The maximum normal stresses (+112/-56.0 MPa) occur near the strut connection points.

However, these values are low in comparison to the fibre strength of Twintex™ (+269/-178 MPa) and are within the desired strength safety factors for the blade. For the core, the maximum principal stress (1.39 MPa) and shear stress (0.78 MPa) are below the tensile strength (1.6 MPa) and shear strength (1.1 MPa) for the PET foam. For all cases, no damage or fracture in the skin or core was predicted. The blade tip deflection of 35 mm is within acceptable limits.

Table 2. Results of the structural analysis.

Loadcase	Max. skin tensile stress (MPa)	Max. skin compressive stress (MPa)	Max. skin in-plane stress (MPa)	Max core principal stress (MPa)	Max core shear stress (MPa)	Max. tip displacement (mm)
Case 1	37.41	16	3.6	0.48	0.27	11
Case 2	112	56	9.84	1.39	0.78	35

Figure 14. Stress contours and deformation shape of the blade for design load case 2 (deformation magnified by a factor of 5).

CONCLUSIONS

Preliminary work on the design, finite element analysis and manufacture of a proposed thermoplastic composite sandwich structure blade for a 5 kW vertical axis wind turbine has been presented. The initial design was analysed using a sub-scale prototype of the blade to prove-out the one-step vacuum moulding process and validate the finite element methodology. The potential use of a simple, low cost, out of autoclave vacuum moulding process for consolidating a complete thermoplastic composite sandwich blade has been demonstrated. The 24 hour manufacturing cycle could be decreased significantly with a water cooled tool which would make the process more industrially attractive. The finite element methodology has been validated for predictive analysis. The simulation results for a bending test on the sub-scale blade showed good correlation with test results for force-displacement history and most major damage modes. However, further refinement of the model is required for the accurate simulation of ultimate failure in the form of skin delamination and skin-core debonding. A modal analysis of the full scale blade showed its fundamental frequency to be sufficiently high to avoid oscillation coupling with the rotational frequency. Finite element models were

developed for evaluating the structural performance of the full-scale blade under two load cases, storm loading and loss of load. In general, the thermoplastic composites sandwich blade is shown to satisfy the stipulated design criteria for strength, tip deflection and damage.

Future work will involve further optimisation of the vacuum moulding process. In addition, a more detailed and accurate finite element model capable of simulating skin delamination and skin-core debonding is being developed.

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